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POLITICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL DETERMINANTS OF EU INTEGRATION IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC AND SLOVAKIA

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***Abstract.** The article provides a comparative analysis of the integration of the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic into the European Union, focusing on differences in initial conditions, political development, administrative capacity, and the fulfillment of accession criteria. Particular attention is paid to the unequal starting positions of the two states after the dissolution of Czechoslovakia, including disparities in foreign policy experience, institutional continuity, and human resources. The study examines the implementation of the EU White Paper, national strategies for legislative harmonization, and the influence of political leadership on the pace and quality of reforms. Based on European Commission Opinions, Progress Reports, and National Programs for the Adoption of the Acquis, the article highlights the reasons for Slovakia's delayed accession negotiations and the Czech Republic's inclusion in the first wave of enlargement. The analysis demonstrates that despite temporary setbacks and differing trajectories, both countries eventually achieved significant progress and became leaders among Central and Eastern European candidates for EU membership by 2004.*

Keywords: European Union enlargement; Slovakia; Czech Republic; European integration; accession process; *acquis communautaire*; political criteria; legislative harmonization; Central and Eastern Europe.

**ПОЛІТИЧНІ ТА ІНСТИТУЦІЙНІ ДЕТЕРМІНАНТИ ІНТЕГРАЦІЇ
ЧЕСЬКОЇ РЕСПУБЛІКИ ТА СЛОВАЦЬКОЇ РЕСПУБЛІКИ ДО
ЄВРОПЕЙСЬКОГО СОЮЗУ**

Анотація. У статті здійснено комплексний порівняльний аналіз процесу інтеграції Чеської Республіки та Словацької Республіки до Європейського Союзу з акцентом на політичні та інституційні чинники, що визначали темпи й результати євроінтеграційного поступу обох держав. Особливу увагу приділено різним стартовим умовам, у яких опинилися Чехія та Словаччина після розпаду Чехословацької Федеративної Республіки, зокрема рівню інституційної спадковості, наявності кадрового потенціалу, досвіду здійснення зовнішньої політики та функціонування державного управління. Проаналізовано вплив внутрішньополітичного розвитку, позицій політичних еліт і якості демократичних інститутів на оцінки Європейської комісії та перебіг переговорного процесу.

У роботі розглянуто реалізацію положень Білої книги ЄС, національні програми гармонізації законодавства, а також Національні програми з упровадження *acquis communautaire*. Показано, що хоча обидві держави досягли загалом задовільних результатів в економічній сфері, ключовим чинником диференційованого підходу Європейського Союзу стала відповідність політичним критеріям членства. Недотримання демократичних стандартів у Словацькій Республіці в середині 1990-х років зумовило її виключення з першої хвилі розширення ЄС, тоді як Чеська Республіка була запрошена до переговорів раніше, попри стримане ставлення її політичного керівництва до членства в Євросоюзі.

Окремо наголошено на трансформаційній ролі зміни політичного курсу у Словаччині після 1998 року, що дозволило країні в стислі терміни подолати попередні відставання, активізувати реформи та суттєво покращити свої позиції у щорічних звітах Європейської комісії. Зроблено висновок, що досвід Чехії та Словаччини засвідчує вирішальне значення політичної волі, стабільності демократичних інститутів і ефективності державного управління для успішної інтеграції постсоціалістичних країн до Європейського Союзу.

Ключові слова: розширення Європейського Союзу; Словаччина; Чехія; європейська інтеграція; процес приєднання; *acquis communautaire*; політичні критерії; гармонізація законодавства; Центральна та Східна Європа.

Formulation of the Problem. The enlargement of the European Union toward Central and Eastern Europe raised complex political, institutional, and administrative challenges for post-socialist states. Despite similar historical backgrounds and simultaneous emergence as independent countries after the dissolution of Czechoslovakia, the Czech Republic and the Slovak Republic demonstrated markedly different trajectories in their integration into the European Union. These differences were reflected in the timing of accession negotiations, assessments by the European

Commission, and the overall pace of reforms. The problem addressed in this article lies in identifying and explaining the key political and institutional factors that determined these divergent integration paths, as well as in assessing the extent to which initial conditions, domestic political developments, and administrative capacity influenced compliance with EU accession criteria. Understanding these determinants is essential for explaining differentiated outcomes within the EU enlargement process and for drawing broader conclusions applicable to other candidate and aspiring member states.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. Recent academic research on European Union enlargement and the integration of Central and Eastern European countries has paid considerable attention to the political, institutional, and normative dimensions of the accession process. Scholars such as F. Schimmelfennig and U. Sedelmeier emphasize the role of EU conditionality and the effectiveness of political criteria in shaping domestic reforms in candidate states, arguing that compliance largely depends on the credibility of membership incentives and domestic political costs. Other studies focus on the Copenhagen criteria as the central framework guiding enlargement, highlighting the primacy of democratic governance, rule of law, and minority protection in EU assessments.

A number of comparative works examine post-socialist transformations in Central Europe, including the Czech Republic and Slovakia, stressing the importance of institutional continuity, administrative capacity, and elite consensus for successful European integration. Researchers note that the Czech Republic benefited from stronger state institutions and a more stable political environment in the early 1990s, while Slovakia faced challenges related to democratic backsliding and weaker governance structures. At the same time, more recent publications underline Slovakia's rapid reform progress after 1998 as evidence of the transformative power of EU accession conditionality.

Policy-oriented analyses and European Commission reports constitute another significant body of literature. Annual Progress Reports, Opinions, and Partnership Documents are widely used as primary sources for evaluating compliance with accession criteria and monitoring reform dynamics. These documents have been extensively analyzed by scholars to assess the interaction between domestic politics

and external EU pressure. However, despite the substantial volume of research, there remains a need for integrated comparative studies that systematically assess political and institutional determinants of EU integration in closely related states with shared historical legacies. This article seeks to contribute to this gap by offering a focused comparative analysis of the Czech and Slovak experiences.

The Purposes of the Article. The purpose of this article is to conduct a comparative analysis of the European Union integration processes of the Czech Republic and the Slovak Republic, with particular emphasis on political and institutional determinants. The article aims to examine the impact of initial post-independence conditions, the role of political leadership and democratic governance, and the effectiveness of administrative and legislative reforms in meeting EU accession requirements. Additionally, the study seeks to evaluate the influence of European Commission assessments, National Programs for the Adoption of the Acquis, and Progress Reports on shaping national reform agendas. Through this analysis, the article intends to identify common patterns and key differences in the integration experiences of both countries and to contribute to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms driving successful EU enlargement.

The main material presentation. When assessing the specific features of the integration process of the Slovak Republic (SR) and the Czech Republic (CR) into the European Union, it is first necessary to note the less favorable starting position of Slovakia compared to the Czech Republic. A very important circumstance should be taken into account here: unlike its immediate neighbors, Slovakia, for understandable reasons, did not have a long-standing tradition of conducting foreign policy, which is an integral attribute of an independent state, and therefore had virtually no experience in this field. Moreover, Prague, the capital of Czechoslovakia, concentrated all central state authorities as well as ministries equipped with qualified specialists and technical resources. After the dissolution of the Czech and Slovak Federal Republic, the property of the former federation was divided between the Czech Republic and the Slovak Republic in a ratio of 2:1. Following the emergence of two sovereign states, all citizens of the former Czechoslovakia were given the opportunity to freely choose their citizenship. Many politicians, diplomats, Czechs and Slovaks who had worked in

Prague for a long time decided to continue their careers in the Czech Republic. Consequently, Slovaks who remained in Czech institutions adopted Czech citizenship. As a result, Slovakia began to experience an acute shortage of qualified personnel in this area. In the political sphere of the Slovak Republic, especially during the first years of its existence, many dilettantes appeared – individuals who had no experience in the field, lacked knowledge of foreign languages, did not possess appropriate education, and sometimes were unfamiliar with diplomatic protocol. These individuals repeatedly became members of delegations participating in negotiations with representatives of the European Union, which caused justified irritation and a biased attitude toward Slovakia.

These facts, of course, cannot justify the mistakes made by the Slovak side during the integration process into the European Union; nevertheless, they must be taken into consideration.

To implement the provisions of the White Paper on the harmonization of legislation in the field of the internal market, developed in 1995 with due regard to the specific conditions of Slovakia and the Czech Republic, the governments of both countries were required to prepare programs for adopting the norms contained in the White Paper. In this respect, the difference in the approaches of the SR and CR governments to fulfilling EU conditions became particularly evident. Despite the fact that Czech Prime Minister V. Klaus never expressed enthusiasm regarding EU membership, the Czech Republic fulfilled its commitments in a timely manner. Czech politicians and experts of relevant institutions immediately began work on adapting national legislation to EU norms, and already in the spring of 1996 the Government of the Czech Republic approved the document *“Priorities for Implementing the White Paper in the Czech Republic”* [1].

In Slovakia, due to certain features of its internal situation, “there was no need to hurry.” Similar documents – *“National Program for the Approximation of Legal Norms of the SR and the EU in the Area of the Internal Market”* [2] and *“Strategy of the Slovak Republic Aimed at Implementing European Union Law in Priority Areas”* [3] (better known as *“Definition of National Priorities”*) – were adopted by the Government of

the Slovak Republic only on February 4, 1997, almost two years after the publication of the White Paper.

The integration process of both countries into the EU was significantly influenced by the beliefs and views of individuals holding leading positions in Slovakia and the Czech Republic. For example, V. Mečiar, who at that time served as Prime Minister of Slovakia, repeatedly emphasized that he, together with the Slovak people, aspired to Slovakia's earliest possible accession to the European Union. To demonstrate this commitment, Slovakia submitted its application at the first opportunity – during the European Council meeting in Cannes on June 27, 1995. Through such haste, Mečiar sought to show European officials his firm conviction regarding Slovakia's rapid accession to the EU. However, Slovakia's internal development did not correspond to the ambitious plans of its leadership, which was reflected in the content of the European Commission's Opinion on Slovakia's application.

The Opinion stated that in the economic sphere, in terms of readiness to assume the obligations associated with EU membership, the Slovak Republic had achieved a satisfactory level and, in general (despite some shortcomings), had fulfilled the required conditions. However, Slovakia was criticized for administrative and legal unpreparedness for EU membership and, more importantly, for failure to meet political criteria (restriction of opposition rights, insufficient efforts to combat corruption within government structures, lack of guarantees for judicial independence, unresolved issues concerning national minorities). As a result, Slovakia became the only associated country that failed to meet the political conditions. Disagreement with this assessment was expressed in the document *“Position of the Government of the Slovak Republic on the European Commission's Opinion on Slovakia's Application for EU Membership”* [4], in which the Slovak side argued that the Commission had somewhat exaggerated the importance of certain political problems. Nevertheless, failure to meet political criteria had negative consequences for Slovakia – its exclusion from the group of countries with which accession negotiations began in 1998. Slovakia was invited to the negotiating table only in February 2000.

The situation with the Czech Republic was different. The Czech Republic submitted its application for EU membership much later than Slovakia and later than

most Central and Eastern European countries – on January 23, 1996 – thereby signaling a lack of urgency regarding accession (a position influenced by Prime Minister V. Klaus). This impression was reinforced by statements about the unpopularity, fragility, and complexity of the EU contained in the Memorandum attached to the application [5]. Nevertheless, the European Commission’s Opinion on the Czech application was far more favorable than that on Slovakia’s. In fulfilling political criteria, the Czech side encountered no serious problems (only restrictions on press freedom and minority rights were noted). In the economic sphere, readiness to assume EU obligations, as well as administrative and legal preparedness, the Czech Republic achieved satisfactory results, with only a limited number of remarks. Unlike Slovakia, the Czech Republic was included among the countries with which the EU began accession negotiations on March 31, 1998 – the so-called “first wave” of EU enlargement.

Nevertheless, neither the Czech Republic nor Slovakia managed to fulfill all pre-accession conditions, which led to the development of the Partnership Programs.

In addition to similar problems, each republic faced its own specific difficulties, which the other managed to overcome more successfully.

In the short term, the Czech Republic undertook to focus on tasks such as restructuring the aluminum sector in line with EU requirements; improving tender legislation; adopting a civil service law; implementing additional training programs for judges in EU law; amending laws on technical product standards, internal market supervision, and recognition of professional qualifications; approximating legislation in telecommunications, competition policy, regional development, and insurance; strengthening the Securities Commission; harmonizing tax legislation; and adopting norms protecting shareholder rights and personal data.

In the medium term, the Czech Republic faced challenges in monitoring public debt, developing a medium-term fiscal strategy, supporting the private sector, liberalizing energy prices, reforming healthcare financing and the pension system. The EU also required the Czech Republic to complete legal harmonization in personal data protection, free movement of goods and persons, establish food safety control systems, modernize meat and dairy facilities, strengthen efforts against drug trafficking and human trafficking, ensure nuclear safety at Dukovany and Temelín plants, coordinate

oil reserves, enhance radiation safety structures, harmonize gender equality norms, improve social security coordination, and establish a guarantee fund for employer insolvency.

In the short term, the Slovak Republic committed itself to ensuring free presidential and parliamentary elections, local elections, and involving opposition representatives in parliamentary oversight bodies. In the economic sphere, Slovakia aimed to define medium-term priorities, address trade imbalances, maintain macroeconomic stability, and reduce the budget deficit. Slovakia also pledged to strengthen border management, reform administrative structures, reinforce environmental and veterinary authorities, and harmonize legislation with EU standards in certification, veterinary, and phytosanitary areas.

In the medium term, Slovakia faced difficulties in constitutional compliance, opposition rights, judicial independence, and democratic institutions. The European Commission required Slovakia to set economic priorities regularly, meet Copenhagen economic and financial criteria, improve budget oversight coordination, complete legal harmonization in financial services, audiovisual policy, and energy, comply with environmental standards in agriculture, improve asylum legislation, develop a long-term energy strategy, complete the Mochovce nuclear plant in accordance with international safety standards, and adopt a program for closing the Bohunice plant. Slovakia also committed to investing in transport infrastructure, expanding trans-European networks, developing the labor market, and strengthening law enforcement and anti-organized crime bodies.

The comparison of problem areas shows that similarities primarily concerned large-scale, long-term reforms (judicial reform, minority issues, legal harmonization), while differences were more specific and sectoral. Since 1998, *acquis screening* – comparative analysis of associated states' legislation with EU law – has been conducted [6]. Slovakia and the Czech Republic began from different starting positions: Slovakia in the second wave and the Czech Republic in the first wave of enlargement.

A crucial stage in integration was the development of National Programs for the Adoption of the *Acquis* (NPAA). At the initiative of the Czech government, three additional documents were included in the Czech NPAA: “*Assessment of Economic*

Policy Priorities,” “*Pact against Organized Crime,*” and “*Assessment of the Internal Market of the Czech Republic.*” These documents aimed to signal readiness to exceed EU requirements.

Another difference concerned timeframes. Slovakia’s NPAA was revised again in 2002, while the Czech NPAA was designed to remain valid until January 1, 2003, when the Czech Republic expected to become an EU member.

Annual European Commission Progress Reports [7] became a key evaluation tool. The Czech report for 1998 was positive, but the 1999 report [8] was highly critical due to economic crisis and focus on NATO accession. Subsequent reports showed improvement [9; 10]. For Slovakia, the 1998 report was negative, but after political change in 1998, assessments improved significantly, culminating in the highly positive 2002 report, which ranked Slovakia among the best-performing candidates.

Both Slovakia and the Czech Republic prioritized meeting accession conditions by 2004. Despite obstacles, both countries ranked among the leaders of Central and Eastern Europe in EU accession. Although by the end of 2001 the Czech Republic was considered more prepared, the final European Commission report showed that Slovakia had overtaken it.

Conclusions. The comparative analysis of the European Union integration processes of the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic demonstrates that the pace and quality of accession were largely determined by initial institutional conditions, political development, and the capacity of state administrations to implement reforms. Following the dissolution of Czechoslovakia, the Czech Republic benefited from greater institutional continuity, administrative experience, and human resources, which facilitated the early harmonization of legislation with EU norms and ensured more favorable assessments by the European Commission. In contrast, Slovakia’s weaker starting position, combined with internal political instability and deficiencies in democratic governance during the 1990s, significantly delayed its accession negotiations.

The study confirms that compliance with political criteria was a decisive factor in the EU’s differentiation between candidate states. While both countries demonstrated comparable economic potential and the ability to adopt the *acquis communautaire*,

Slovakia's failure to meet political standards resulted in its exclusion from the first wave of enlargement. However, political change after 1998 enabled Slovakia to rapidly overcome earlier shortcomings, implement institutional reforms, and significantly improve its performance in subsequent Progress Reports.

Ultimately, despite divergent trajectories and temporary asymmetries in preparedness, both the Czech Republic and the Slovak Republic succeeded in fulfilling the accession criteria and became EU members in 2004. The experience of these two states illustrates that initial disadvantages can be mitigated through sustained political commitment, institutional reform, and effective alignment with EU requirements, underscoring the transformative role of the EU accession process for post-socialist countries.

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